

The Structure of Nominal Phraseological Units of English, Russian and Uzbek Languages

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Abstract: This research is aimed at a comparative study of nominal phraseological units of English, Russian, Uzbek languages. Nominal phraseological units are phrases or expressions that consist of two or more words that, when combined, create a different meaning from the literal definitions of its individual words. Nominal phraseological units in Russian and Uzbek languages add cultural depth and vividness to the languages, embodying traditional values and expressions. A nominal group is widely regarded as synonymous with noun phrase in other grammatical models. Nominal phraseological units (NPU) in the English language are multi-word expressions or fixed phrases centered around a noun. They convey a meaning that is not directly inferred from the meanings of their individual words. These units are common in English and often have idiomatic or figurative meanings.

Key points: concept, nominal group, nominal phraseological units, cultural significance, idiomatic meaning, noun-centered, fixed structure, phraseological fusions, phraseological unities, phraseological combinations, cultural expressions, uzbek scholars.

INTRODUCTION

In linguistics, phraseological units serve a crucial role as they offer important insights into cultural values, standards, patterns, and symbols. According to V.N.Telia "Phraseology is the mirror where the humans national and cultural identity is reflected". Telia highlights that phraseological units are linked to cultural and national norms, stereotypes, and myths and the worldview of a particular linguo-cultural community. Phraseological units can relate to numerous subjects such as the customs and traditions of a culture, superstitions, geography, animals, colors, human body parts, nature, and the lifestyles of different nationalities. The idea of phraseological units was developed by linguist S.Balls, who is associated with the French school of linguistics. He referred to the phraseological units as "combinations that have become firmly established in the language". The vocabulary richness of any language relies not only on how new words are created but also on the enduring idioms it can develop. The discipline that examines the realm of those units is known as phraseology.

Phraseological units are considered a subsystem of language. Phraseological units cannot be created spontaneously in conversation; instead, they are used as pre-formed expressions. The lexical elements of phraseological units are fixed and non-motivated, their meaning cannot be inferred from the meaning of their parts, and they do not allow changes or substitutions of their lexical elements. [7,3]

In systematic functional grammar, a nominal group consists of a collection of words that denote or characterize an entity, for example "The handsome old English police inspector who was sitting at

the table with Mr. Tompson” can be understood as a nominal group (a description of a person), which serves as the subject of the information transfer and as the someone being identified as “Mr. Tompson” A nominal group is commonly seen as equivalent to a noun phrase in various grammatical frameworks.

Nominal phraseological units are idiomatic expressions made up of a noun along with other words, frequently incorporating a verb or adjective. They are often utilized in daily speech and possess a figurative significance that differs from the actual meaning of the terms. The key component of nominal phraseological units is a noun. They have fixed structure: They are typically not subject to major grammatical changes. They have an idiomatic meaning. The meaning is often non-literal and must be understood as a whole. Here are several instances of nominal phraseological units in English, Russian, and Uzbek languages.

1. A piece of cake- an activity that is simple to accomplish
2. A heart of gold-a generous and kind individual
3. A breath of fresh air-something new and refreshing
4. Душа в штаны- a soul in pants (someone who is extremely furious)
5. Белая ворона- a white crow (an individual or thing that is unique or rare)
6. Взять за глаза- to take by the eyes (to deceive or manipulate)
7. Гора с горы сорочка- a mountain from a shirt (something that appears big or challenging, but turns out to be simple)
8. Azot tanho baliq po'stida- nitrogen is only found in fish scales (something that is uncommon or difficult to locate)
9. Xonadonga qushtan ilma- if you don't kill the snake, it will transform into a dragon (if you ignore a small issue, it will become a big problem) [4,3]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study of nominal phraseological units falls under the broader fields of phraseology, which has been explored by numerous linguists and scholars. These individuals have contributed foundational theories, classifications, and methodologies for analyzing phraseological units across languages. Charles Bally, a prominent Swiss linguist and one of the early contributors to phraseology, did not specifically define nominal phraseological units as a distinct category. However, his work laid the foundation for the study of phraseological combinations in general. Bally's approach to phraseology focused on fixed expressions and their stylistic function in language. Bally introduced the term “phraseological combinations” to describe fixed or semi-fixed multi-word expressions that carry specific stylistic and emotional connotations. According to him “Fixed expressions, including Nominal phraseological units, enhance expressiveness in language. [5]

According to a Russian linguist Victor Vinogradov who significantly advanced phraseology: “Nominal phraseological units typically fall under phraseological fusions and phraseological unities, as they often carry idiomatic meanings or fixed combinations” [3,350]. Vinogradov categorized phraseological units based on their semantic unity and structural characteristics. His classification includes:

Phraseological fusions-Completely indivisible and idiomatic expressions (example: crocodile tears).

Phraseological unities-Expressions where the overall meaning is figurative but partially linked to the literal meaning (example: to spill the beans)

Phraseological combinations-Partially fixed expressions where one word has a restricted collocational use (example: make a decision)

Vinogradov emphasized the idiomatic nature of phraseological units, where the meaning of the whole is not deducible from its parts. For NPUs, the central noun often carries a metaphorical or

symbolic meaning (example: storm in a teacup). Next scholar Alexander Koonin developed the Koonin Theory of Phraseology, emphasizing the systematic nature of phraseological units. He analyzed idiomatic expressions in English, including NPUs, within a linguistic framework. His contributions provided a comprehensive theoretical framework that has shaped modern phraseological studies. Koonin defined phraseological units as stable, reproducible combinations of words with partially transferred meaning. This definition includes nominal units that often involve a noun as their core. Koonin's work remains a cornerstone in the study of phraseology. His monograph on English phraseology, as well as his research on idiomaticity and stability, continues to guide scholars analyzing NPUs and other types of fixed expressions in various languages. [2,59]

The collection of Uzbek phraseology is abundant with national and borrowed, as well as terminological and non-terminological phraseological units, similar to phraseology in the English language. Uzbek and Russian researchers and scholars have been working hard on the field of phraseological units. The theoretical concerns of the Uzbek phraseology were pointed out in the works of Y.Polivanov. He dealt with the phraseology of the Russian and some oriental languages and offered the idea of separating phraseology as an independent linguistic branch. As Polivanov stresses, a new forming phraseology branch should take place for lexicology as important as syntax for morphology. [8,4] In this area, particularly, the contribution of Sh. Rakhmatullaev, B.Yuldoshev, Abdumurod Mamatov, Abdugafur Mamatov, Sh. Almamatova is excellent. Sh. Rakhmatullaev investigated semantic characteristics and relationships on form and content in phraseological units, and he also created an explanatory dictionary of Uzbek phraseologisms in a monographic way. B. Yuldoshev examined the stylistic features of phraseology, and A.Mamatov contributed in the advancement of Uzbek phraseology by his surveys on formation of phraseological units. S.Kenesboyev studies the concepts of V.Vinogradov when he defines the content of phraseology, proves differences between proverbs and sayings. When he classifies phraseological units as a phraseological mixture, a phraseological entire and a phraseological compound. S.Muratov points that phraseologisms are distinguished from free word combinations according to the following features:

- 1) semantic integrity;
- 2) figurativeness;
- 3) having an extended sense.[10,8]

So that, the phraseology is in replete with proverbs, sayings and aphorisms because they all have the property of stability, unlikely it has some features which make it different from them. Sh.Rakhmatullaev regards a phraseology as a lexical unit consisting of more than one lexical stem, equal to a word combination or a clause by its structure, semantically equivalent to a word, and wholly denoting an over figurative meaning.[13,2] A.Khojiev considers that a phraseology is a lexical unit which is equal to a word combination or a clause by its structure, semantically a whole entire, delivering a meaning in an integrated way, not created while a speech process, but introduced into language as a ready-made item; and is a type of stable word combinations with a figurative meaning. 4 Uzbek linguistics who have contributed to the development of this field are the followings: A.Isaev, O.Nazarov, Sh.Usmonova, Sh.Nazirova, H.Alimova. There is one of the branches of lexicology that studies phraseological units, idioms words and group of words, which are readymade and are mostly applied both in a written and oral language. They are the followings:

- phraseological units
- proverbs
- aphorisms “Do`ppisini osmonga otmoq”– xursand. It refers to a psychological condition when people are glad and thrilled. However, there are some exceptions that cannot be expressed by one word: For instance, bog`dan kelsa, tog`dan kelmoq – suhbatdoshning gapiga hech qanday aloqasi yo`q gap so`z aytmoq

Phraseological units can be inquired by one interrogation and replied too. Phraseological idioms and units are scrutinized completely in the sentence but not separately word. [14,4]

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Nominal phraseological units are established word combinations that convey a particular meaning in the English language. These units consist of a main noun and one or more associated words, like adjectives or prepositions. They are often referred to as idioms, collocations, or fixed expressions. One element that contributes to the depth and intricacy of nominal phraseological units is the tone they express. Depending on the situation and the person speaking, these units can convey a vocal tone that communicates various emotions, such as humor, sarcasm, or seriousness. For instance, the expression “hit the books” can be used in a fun way to motivate someone to study in a more serious tone to refer to studying diligently. The tone of voice linked to nominal phraseological units enriches the English language, facilitating more effective and diverse communication. Here some more examples of nominal phraseological units in English language:

1. Noun Phrases: “The Big Apple”- a nickname for New York City;
2. Idiomatic Expressions: “A blessing in disguise”- Something that seems bad at first but results in something good.
3. Collocations: “Strong coffee”- a common way to describe coffee that has a rich flavor;
“Heavy rain”-a typical phrase used to describe a significant amount of rainfall.
4. Set Phrases: “The bottom line”- the most important point or conclusion;
“A double-edged sword”- something that has both positive and negative consequences.
5. Proverbs and Saying “Actions speak louder than words”- what someone does is more important than what they say;
“The early bird catches the worm”- those who start early have an advantage.

The nominal phraseological units play a crucial role in understanding the nuances of the English language, since they frequently convey meanings that are not immediately apparent from the separate words. [3,350]

Nominal phraseological units play a crucial role in the Russian language, including a broad spectrum of expressions and idioms frequently used in everyday conversation. They have an essential function in the Russian language, enriching discussions and enabling more imaginative and expressive interactions. Nominal phraseological units frequently represent cultural and historical customs and can differ significantly based on the region or social group that employs. They may also serve to convey emotions, attitudes and beliefs in a succinct and impactful way. Thus, they are not only a fundamental component of the language but also a mirror of Russian culture and lifestyle. Gaining proficiency in these units is crucial for anyone aiming to thoroughly comprehend and interact with the Russian language, in both formal and casual situations. These phraseological units enhance the vibrancy and depth of the language while also showcasing the distinctive mindset and worldview of native Russian speakers. [9,175] They exist in different styles like proverbs, sayings, colloquialisms, and slang. Some common examples include “выпить чашку чая” (to have a cup of tea), which means to chat or “брать быка за рога” (to take the bull by the horns) which is used to describe taking decisive action, or “Кот в мешке” literally “a cat in a bag”, meaning something that is bought or accepted without being seen or examined first, akin to “a pig in a poke”, “Держать камень за пазухой” literally “to hold a stone in one’s bosom”, meaning to harbor ill intentions or to be secretly hostile, “Собака на сене” literally “a dog in the hay”, referring to someone who prevents others from enjoying something they themselves do not want, similar to the English expression “a dog in the manger”, “Как две капли воды” literally “like two drops of water”, meaning two things or people that are very similar or identical, last but not least “Говорить на одном языке” literally “to speak the same language”, meaning to have a mutual understanding or to be in agreement and other examples.[1,1414] Due to their cultural significance, understanding and using nominal phraseological units is essential for effective communication and a deeper understanding of Russian language and culture.

Nominative phraseological units of the Uzbek language can be derived from realia, denoting objects or phenomena of everyday life. For example, the phraseological unit “kulla”, which literally means “plough”, is used to mean “hardworking, diligent”. Another example of this unit is “Ko’z ochib yumguncha”- Literally translates to “before you can blink”, meaning something happens very quickly.

The nominative function of phraseological units pertains to their connection with real-world objects and situations, as well as the use of these units to substitute for those objects during communication.

CONCLUSION

Nominal phraseological units represent a crucial and dynamic aspect of linguistic expression, combining structural stability with semantic richness. Their unique characteristics-such as fixedness, idiomaticity, and cultural specificity-highlight the interplay between language and society. Through their use, speakers convey not only literal meanings but also emotions, attitudes, and cultural nuances.

The theoretical frameworks established by linguists like Charles Bally, Viktor Vinogradov, and Alexander Koonin have laid a solid foundation for understanding the intricacies of NPUs. These frameworks emphasize their role in enriching language and fostering communication efficiency by condensing complex ideas into memorable, fixed expressions. Moreover, NPUs reflect the evolution of language, serving as a repository of historical and cultural heritage.

Future studies can explore the contrastive analysis of NPUs across languages, their cognitive processing, and their adaptability in modern communication, including digital media. By continuing to investigate NPUs, linguists can deepen our understanding of how language shapes thought and reflects the diverse experiences of human communities.

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